

An Investigation into the Optimum Loading of Recycled Wind Turbine Blades Blended with Industrial Polyolefin Waste Using Conventional Hot Melt Extruders

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Conor Cleary

Department of Mechanical, Polymer & Design

Engineering and Informatics

Technological University of the Shannon

Midlands

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Candidate's Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis consists of my own work, unless otherwise stated, and has not previously been submitted to the Technological University of the Shannon, Midlands or any other university.

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Abstract

The main focus of this study was to investigate the optimum loading levels of recycled polyolefins combined with industrial composites (wind turbine blades). Aspects of industrial waste are 100% recyclable but are not recycled because of unfavourable mixes in blends such as colour or additives (fibres, nanomaterials, foaming agents). These blends often end up in landfills or incineration. The aim of this research has been to determine the optimum loading percentages for incorporating industrial olefins that would go to landfill with other industrial composites into a useable product with value and purpose, establishing performance-based guidelines for optimal composition ranges.

The study investigated the mechanical properties and processing characteristics of composite materials produced from mixed polyethylene waste (MPE) and shredded wind turbine blade waste (WTB). The study examined the effect of repeated compounding processes on various composite olefin blends to assess the influence of shear on blend performance. Systematic mechanical characterization was conducted on composite blends containing 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 60% WTB by weight in an MPE matrix using conventional twin screw extrusion and injection moulding processes.

Tensile testing revealed that ultimate tensile strength decreased by 29% (from 5.479 to 3.907 MPa) while Young's modulus increased by 115% (from 1000 to 2150 MPa) as WTB content increased from 0% to 60%. Impact testing identified a critical transition threshold between 10-20% WTB loading, where impact strength dropped dramatically from >5.5J to 0.72J at maximum loading, accompanied by a 90% reduction in elongation at break. The results demonstrated that WTB components act as rigid inclusions rather than effective reinforcements due to poor interfacial bonding with the polyolefin matrix.

Surface morphology analysis revealed progressive texturing and fibre visibility with increasing WTB content, consistent with the observed mechanical property degradation. Despite these limitations, the research successfully demonstrated that up to 60% wind turbine blade waste can be incorporated into polyolefin waste streams, creating materials with enhanced flexural performance, making them suitable for structural applications that require enhanced bending strength while diverting substantial waste volumes from landfills.

Research Problem

Aspects of industrial waste are 100% recyclable but are not recycled because of unfavourable mixes in blends such as colour or additives (fibres, nanomaterials, foaming agents). These blends often end up in landfills or incineration. However, limited knowledge exists regarding the optimum loading levels for incorporating recycled wind turbine blade waste into industrial polymer waste streams while maintaining acceptable mechanical properties for commercial applications.

Objectives

To develop various blends incorporating industrial olefins that would go to landfill and incorporating other industrial composites into a useable product with value, by determining the optimum loading levels for recycled wind turbine blade waste blended with industrial polyolefin waste using conventional hot melt processing, and to establish performance-based recommendations for optimal composition ranges.

Scope

- Complete a literature review on what is currently being done with industrial olefins and other industrial composites
- Produce various w/w% blends of industrial olefins and industrial composites
- Injection mould and develop test samples
- Carry out mechanical characterisation on all test samples (tensile, flexural, impact)

1. Literature Review

1.1 Introduction

As more attention is given to circular economy ideas, it's becoming clear that the old 'take make dispose' model no longer works. Instead, industries are being pushed to manage waste more responsibly. Moving from a linear to a circular economy is essential for cutting down on plastic pollution and finding ways to reuse and get value from waste, rather than just throwing it away [1]. Current linear models, characterised by the "take make waste" approach, are becoming seen as unsustainable, especially for polymer based products that may remain in the environment for long periods of time. This trend is consistent with the broader push towards sustainable energy systems, which emphasises minimising waste and maximising resource efficiency [2].

Plastic waste has gained a lot of focus in academic and political debates as a global problem that requires an urgent solution [3]. The long life of polymer materials in the environment presents unique challenges for waste management systems worldwide. Traditional waste management, such as open burning, landfilling, and incineration, contribute major greenhouse gas emissions and result in economic loss [4]. These traditional practices not only waste the potential of polymer materials, but they also drain limited natural resources. In much the same way that sustainable energy systems like solar, wind, and geothermal have reimagined how we generate power with minimal harm, we need innovative waste solutions that reduce environmental impact and recapture value [2].

The circular economy model is a key strategy for sustainability, redesigning material flows and production systems. Unlike linear models that treat materials as disposable commodities, circular systems aim towards the continuous circulation of resources through multiple use cycles. This principle mirrors the advancements in energy storage solutions, such as batteries and pumped hydro storage that promote energy efficiency and help lessen dependence on limited natural resources [2]. Global industrialization and too much dependence on non-renewable energy sources have led to an increase in solid waste and climate change, calling for strategies to implement a circular economy in all sectors to reduce carbon emissions by 45% by 2030 and achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 [5].

Applying circular economy principles to polymer waste management requires creative solutions that tackle both technical challenges and economic limitations. Older methods of waste solution like landfilling and mechanical recycling are increasingly viewed as insufficient to meet the scale and complexity of the issue [6]. Advanced recycling technologies and material

recovery systems are now becoming essential components of sustainable waste management, much like how the integration of smart grids and energy management systems is critical for optimizing renewable energy use [2]. These systems ensure that waste is transformed into valuable resources, reducing the need for virgin materials and lowering overall environmental impact.

The scale of the global plastic waste crisis highlights how important it is that sustainable waste management practices are implemented without delay. The present world is now facing the challenge of proper management and resource recovery of the enormous amount of plastic waste [7]. To effectively implement circular economy principles majorly coordinated efforts need to be made across industrial sectors, supported by appropriate policy frameworks and recycling technologies. Similarly, the transition to sustainable energy systems relies on policy incentives, public awareness, and technological advancements to overcome barriers such as high initial costs and infrastructure limitations [2].

By Combining circular economy principles with sustainable energy strategies, industries can achieve a dual benefit by reducing waste while transitioning to cleaner energy sources. This not only addresses environmental challenges but also fosters economic growth, job creation, and energy security [2].

1.2 Sustainable Energy

1.2.1 Renewable Energy Growth and Environmental Impact

The renewable energy sector worldwide has surged in recent years, highlighting the global need to move beyond reliance on fossil fuels. According to the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), renewable energy capacity reached 4,448 gigawatts (GW) by the end of 2024, representing a massive increase in renewable power capacity during that year alone [8]. This growth trajectory is particularly significant as 92.5% of new power capacity added to the grid in 2024 came from renewable energy sources, indicating that renewable technologies have become the dominant choice for new electricity generation infrastructure, as shown in figures 1 and 2 [8][9].

Renewable share of annual power capacity expansion

Figure 1. Renewable energy capacity [8].

Figure 2. Renewable Power Capacity [8].

The International Energy Agency (IEA) has forecast several critical milestones for the renewable energy sector over the next few years [10]. In 2024, solar PV and wind generation together will outweigh hydropower generation. In 2025, renewables based electricity generation overtakes coal fired. In 2026, wind and solar power generation both surpasses traditional energy sources, marking a fundamental shift in the global energy landscape [10]. This rapid expansion is particularly evident in major economies, where renewables (wind,

solar, hydro, biomass and geothermal) provided over 25% of the total US electricity production in 2024, demonstrating the practical viability of renewable energy systems at scale [11].

The environmental benefits of this renewable energy expansion extend beyond carbon emission reductions. Renewable energy technologies have significantly lower pollution-related environmental impacts per unit of generation than state-of-the-art coal-fired power plants in all of the impact categories examined in comparative studies [12]. This comprehensive environmental benefit includes lower levels of air pollution, reduced water use, and minimized land degradation compared to conventional fossil fuel-based power generation [13]. However, the environmental impact profile of renewable technologies is not uniform across all stages of their operational life, necessitating comprehensive life cycle assessments to fully understand their environmental implications [14].

1.2.2 Life Cycle Considerations in Sustainable Energy Systems

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has become a critical tool for evaluating the true environmental performance of renewable energy technologies [15]. This examines the environmental impacts across all phases of a technology's life cycle, from raw material extraction through manufacturing, operation, and end of life disposal or recycling [14].

The introduction of LCA to renewable energy systems reveals important considerations beyond operational emissions. LCA includes the environmental burdens of converting fuel to useful energy, infrastructure construction, extraction and transportation of fuel, and transport of materials and components [12]. For renewable energy technologies, this means accounting for the environmental costs from start of life to end of life for solar panels, wind turbines, and their infrastructures [13].

Recent studies have examined the application of life cycle assessment (LCA) across the renewable energy sector. In response to the growing demand for sustainable energy, researchers have looked deeper into the environmental impacts of renewable technologies, leading to the classification of LCA studies into categories such as photovoltaic systems, wind energy, solar thermal technologies, and materials used in supporting industries [14]. This structured approach has uncovered both similarities and differences in how renewable energy sectors apply life cycle assessment, emphasising the need for standardized methods [14].

The life cycle perspective is especially relevant when aligning renewable energy systems with circular economy principles. Findings reveal variations driven by combustion efficiency in fossil fuel power plants and operational capacity factors in wind energy systems [12]. This variation highlights how important it is to optimize not only the operational efficiency of renewable energy systems but also their material utilization and end of life management strategies [13].

The connection between renewable energy LCA and waste management becomes relevant when considering the end of life phase of renewable energy infrastructure. Wind turbine blades, solar panels, and battery storage systems all create their own unique challenges for waste management systems and require innovative recycling approaches that align with circular economy principles [15]. Understanding the full life cycle of these systems is key to building truly sustainable energy solutions that reduce environmental impact and improve resource recovery and reuse [14].

1.3 Wind Energy

Wind energy has become one of the most rapidly growing renewable energy technologies, with global capacity expanding immensely over the past decades.

1.3.1 Wind Energy Market Growth and Trends

The global wind energy market has grown significantly in recent years, emerging as a driving force behind the transition to renewable energy sources. In Europe specifically, the capital raised for new wind projects was €33bn in 2024, financing 19.9 GW of new capacity which will be installed over the next few years [16]. The Europe Wind Power Equipment Market is predicted to reach €15.4 billion in 2025 and grow at a CAGR of 11.89% to reach €27.0 billion by 2030 [17]. This demonstrates sustained market confidence and investment momentum within the European context. Market expansion is being driven by several key factors, including policy support, technological improvements, and competitive pricing.

The offshore wind sector represents a particularly dynamic segment of the market, with significant potential for future expansion. Europe is expected to have €58.4 billion floating offshore wind energy market by 2032 due to increasing public and private mergers and contracts accompanied by growing investments across floating offshore wind energy for project deployment [18]. European markets continue to lead in offshore wind development, with Europe expected to install 260 GW of new wind power capacity over 2024-2030, with the

EU-27 installing 200 GW of this – 29 GW a year on average [16]. Ireland has ambitious offshore wind targets, with plans to deliver 20 GW of offshore wind by 2040 and at least 37 GW in total by 2050 [19]

Regional markets are growing and using wind energy differently. Wind already supplies 33% of Ireland's electricity, showing how far it's come in helping power the nation, making it one of the leading wind energy markets in Europe alongside Denmark (56%), Sweden (31%), Germany (30%) and the UK (30%) [16]. Wind Europe expects 15.8 GW of wind capacity to be installed in the EU in 2024, while annual capacity additions are expected to increase significantly over the next five years, rising from an estimated 13 GW in 2024 to nearly 30 GW by 2030 [20].

Global forecasts show the market is expected to perform strongly throughout the projection period, with Europe standing out as a key area of growth. This predicted growth aligns with international climate commitments and the increasing urgency to deploy renewable energy solutions at scale, as illustrated in figure 3 [21].

Figure 3. Energy Source Targets for EU-27 [21].

Both opportunities and challenges are created for the broader energy ecosystem from the wind energy market's expansion. As wind installations increase globally, infrastructure that goes with it, including turbine components and supporting systems, will eventually reach end of life status and create new waste streams that require innovative management approaches. Understanding these market dynamics is essential for developing strategies for wind turbine component recycling and reuse.

1.3.2 Technological Developments in Wind Energy Systems

Wind energy technology in recent years has had some significant advancement in turbine design, materials science, and system integration. Modern wind turbine systems have become sophisticated engineering solutions that can optimize energy capture while also dealing with the challenges of different wind resources and harsh operating environments.

One major development in the technology has been the scaling up of turbine capacity and efficiency. Turbines in the 8–10 MW range accounted for approximately 48.3% of the market share in 2024. However, turbines rated at 12 MW or more are expected to gain traction, driven by continued advancements in turbine technology, including improvements in materials, aerodynamics, and control systems [17]. This shift toward larger turbines showcases the improvements that have been made in materials technology, aerodynamic design, and enhanced structural engineering that allow higher power outputs from individual installations.

Floating offshore wind technology represents one of the most promising areas of technological innovation in the wind energy sector. Using floating platforms to support offshore wind turbines will be necessary for many countries to reach their Net Zero targets, since much of the wind resource is located at water depths that can't accommodate offshore wind turbines [22]. This technology opens new areas for wind energy development. In Ireland, there are floating wind projects under development, including projects with capacities of up to 1 GW, demonstrating the technology's potential in Irish waters [23].

Recently there have been developments in floating wind technology that have marked a major step forward for this sector. Many impressive offshore wind projects across Europe are now in the approval stages, with some reaching capacities of over 500 MW, reflecting that the commercial strength of this technology is growing [24]. Floating wind turbines are expected to be deployed in increasingly deeper waters across Europe in the coming years.

Advancements in materials and manufacturing processes have enabled significant improvements in turbine component performance and durability. Modern wind turbine blades use advanced composite materials that enhance their strength to weight ratios, improve fatigue resistance, and enhance aerodynamic performance [25]. These materials advances have allowed engineers to develop longer blades that can capture more energy from lower wind speeds, expanding the geographic areas suitable for wind energy development.

Control system advancements have improved turbine performance and reliability. Modern wind turbine systems use sophisticated sensors, predictive analytics, and smart machine learning that optimizes turbine operation in real time based on wind conditions, grid requirements, and component health status [26]. These intelligent control systems can operate turbines more efficiently and across a wider range of wind conditions. The systems can also help reduce mechanical stress resulting in extended component life.

Smarter modern Grid technologies are now better equipped to manage the fluctuating output of wind energy, ensuring reliability across power networks. New technology like smarter electronics, better batteries, and improved software are all helping wind energy work more smoothly with the power grid we already have [27]. These technologies help manage the intermittency challenges associated with wind energy while maintaining grid stability and reliability.

The technological evolution of wind energy systems has significant implications for end of life management and recycling strategies. As the size of turbines increases and incorporate more advanced materials, the challenges and opportunities for component recycling and reuse also evolve.

1.4 Wind Turbines

Modern wind turbines have evolved significantly from early designs to become highly optimized machines with the capability of converting wind energy into electricity with remarkable efficiency. Understanding the components, materials, and design evolution of wind turbines is essential when approaching the challenges and opportunities associated with their end of life management and the potential for material recovery.

1.4.1 Wind Turbine Components and Materials

Three primary components that work together to convert kinetic wind energy into electrical power are the rotor assembly, the nacelle, and the support structure including the tower and foundation [28]. Each component comprises of specialized materials selected for their specific performance requirements under challenging operational conditions [29].

1.4.1.1 Rotor Assembly and Blade Materials

The rotor assembly, a combination of the hub and aerodynamic blades, represents the energy capture system of the wind turbine. Modern wind turbine blades are typically manufactured from advanced composite materials that have been optimized to provide a combination of strength, stiffness, and weight characteristics required for efficient energy conversion [28]. The most commonly employed blade materials include glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP), carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP), and increasingly, hybrid composite systems that combine multiple reinforcement types.

GFRP remains the most widely used material in wind turbine blade construction due to its cost and proven performance [29]. However, CFRP has become more popular for the manufacture of larger turbines, where superior stiffness to weight ratios are required to maintain structural integrity while achieving longer blade lengths [30]. The selection between these materials often involves complex trade-offs between performance, cost, and manufacturing considerations, with GFRP offering economic advantages while CFRP provides enhanced mechanical properties at higher costs.

Recent developments in blade materials have focused on bio-based composites and recyclable thermoplastic matrices as the industry seeks to address sustainability challenges associated with conventional thermoset composite systems. These materials are aimed at maintaining the performance characteristics required for wind energy applications while improving end of life recyclability [30]. The manufacturing process for wind turbine blades typically involves hand lay-up methods for smaller production volumes, while larger scale manufacturing increasingly employs automated processes such as resin transfer moulding and vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding to ensure consistent quality and dimensional accuracy.

1.4.1.2 Nacelle Components and Materials

The nacelle houses the critical power conversion components and represents the technological heart of the wind turbine system. Key components within the nacelle include the main bearing, gearbox, generator, power electronics, control systems, and cooling systems [31]. Each component requires specialized materials selected for reliability, efficiency, and longevity under variable loading conditions.

The nacelle structure itself is typically constructed from lightweight materials such as fiberglass or composite materials that provide weather protection while minimizing weight at the top of the tower. The structural frame is generally manufactured from cast steel for the main frame and formed and welded steel for the rear frame, providing the necessary strength and stiffness to support the drivetrain components and transfer loads to the tower [32].

Modern wind turbine gearboxes use high grade steel alloys and specialized bearing materials designed for extreme loading conditions characteristic of wind energy applications. The gearbox design typically employs planetary gear arrangements that provide the necessary speed increase from the low-speed rotor (approximately 30-60 RPM) to the high-speed generator input (1500-1800 RPM) [33].

Generator systems in modern wind turbines often use permanent magnet synchronous generators that incorporate rare earth elements, such as neodymium and dysprosium, to achieve high power densities and efficiency. These materials provide both performance advantages and supply chain challenges, as their availability and cost can significantly impact turbine economics [34].

1.4.1.3 Tower and Foundation Materials

Wind turbine towers provide the structural support system that elevates the rotor and nacelle to heights where wind resources are most favourable. Tower designs traditionally consist of tubular steel construction using galvanized steel sections that are bolted together during installation. Tower heights for modern utility scale turbines typically range from 80-120 meters for onshore installations, with offshore turbines often exceeding 150 meters in total height [35].

Steel tower designs benefit from well established design codes, predictable material properties, and established supply chains. Transportation constraints and material costs have driven interest in alternative tower technologies. Concrete towers and hybrid steel/concrete designs

have gained attention as solutions for achieving greater heights while managing transportation limitations and material costs [36].

Concrete tower technology can have several advantages including reduced material costs, enhanced durability, and the potential for on-site production that eliminates transportation constraints associated with large steel sections. Ultra-high performance concrete (UHPC) and precast concrete segments with post tensioning systems represent advanced approaches to concrete tower construction that can achieve the strength and fatigue resistance required for wind turbine applications [37].

Foundation systems for wind turbines commonly use reinforced concrete spread footings that transfer the turbines load to the underlying soil or rock. Modern foundations for utility scale turbines require substantial concrete volumes, often more than 1000 cubic meters per foundation, along with large quantities of reinforcing steel [38]. The foundation design needs to account for both static loads from the turbine weight and dynamic loads from wind, seismic, and operational forces throughout the turbine's design life.

1.4.2 Design Evolution and Performance Optimization

Wind turbine design has advanced over time as engineers strive to improve blade aerodynamics, ensure structures are both strong and lightweight, and develop advanced control systems. Modern design optimization strategies aim to balance multiple competing objectives including power maximization, load minimization, material efficiency, and lifecycle cost reduction.

1.4.2.1 Aerodynamic Design Evolution and Blade Optimization

The optimization of wind turbine blades aerodynamics has become a significant area for performance enhancement, with researchers now applying highly advanced computer modelling and advanced physical testing to better understand and improve wind turbine blade designs. These methods allow for more accurate predictions and advancements than ever before. Recent research [39] has shown that even slight changes to blade design may result in considerable increases in energy collection and turbine efficiency. The introduction of advanced aerodynamic profiles, variable pitch and twist technologies, and innovative materials

has been a major development for wind power generation giving it a more competitive position in the renewable power sector.

Modern blade design optimizations often use a multidisciplinary approach that considers both aerodynamic performance and structural constraints. The goal is for the blade to generate maximum torque while minimizing its mass [40]. Modern optimization frameworks now use modern software and tools including Defoams software for computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation, TACS for finite element method (FEM) simulation, and integrated platforms such as Open-door in order to optimize the design process.

Blade element momentum (BEM) theory remains a basic approach for initial blade design, while CFD-based optimisation provides significant advances in performance and decreases model uncertainties[41]. The application of Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes models coupled with adjoint methods has demonstrated significant performance improvements, with studies showing torque coefficient increases of up to 22.4% through comprehensive shape optimization involving pitch, twist, and airfoil geometry variables.

A critical point in blade design was the initial use of aerodynamic principles, with pioneers including Albert Betz and Ludwig Prandtl playing crucial roles in this evolution [39]. Betz's Law, which identified the theoretical maximum efficiency for wind turbines, continues to influence blade design and optimization strategies.

1.4.2.2 Advanced Materials and Structural Optimization

The advancements made in materials used in wind turbine construction has been a major influence in enabling larger, more efficient turbines. As longer blades are manufactured, converting structural areas of the blade from fiber-glass to significantly stiffer and lighter carbon fibre makes sense, despite the greater upfront cost [39]. The switch from materials such as steel and basic composites to more modern fibre reinforced polymers has enabled the development of longer blades that are capable of capturing increased amounts of wind energy.

Glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) is still the most common material for wind turbine blade construction due to its proven performance and cost-effectiveness. Despite this, wind blades made of carbon fibre weigh 25% less than those made of traditional fibreglass materials, this allows carbon fibre blades to be longer ,capturing more energy in low wind areas [42]. This weight reduction is particularly significant for large-scale offshore applications where the

implementation of carbon fibre reinforced polymer composite in 60m long wind turbine blades is expected to reduce the blade's weight and the total cost by 38% and 14% respectively [43].

There has been focus recently on producing carbon fibre technology at a more competitive price and also optimizing the performance specifically for wind energy applications. The heavy-tow carbon fibre material performs with 56% more compressive strength when compared on a cost-specific basis to commercial baseline carbon fibre [44]. This is a particularly significant advancement because compressive strength drives material selection in wind turbine applications, where fatigue resistance and long-term durability are essential. Since carbon fibre can cost up to ten times more than glass fibre, improving its cost-to-performance ratio is essential for wider adoption across the European market.

Hybrid composites have become a practical solution that combines the cost effectiveness of glass fibre with the performance advantages of carbon fibre. Techniques have been developed to combine these fibres in the same polymer to create a hybrid material that shares some of the same characteristics as carbon fibre without the increased costs [45]. These hybrid systems allow strategic placement of carbon fibre in regions that experience high stress while maintaining overall cost effectiveness through continued use of glass fibre in less critical areas.

1.4.2.3 Computational Optimization and Design Methodologies

The application of computational optimization methods has transformed the way wind turbines are designed, allowing engineers to systematically navigate intricate design spaces filled with competing objectives and constraints. Advanced optimization technology is required in order to address challenges due to the large and complex design parameter space as well as different operational requirements and environmental conditions [46]. Modern optimization techniques use genetic algorithms, particle swarm methods, and gradient based approaches to fine tune blade shapes and overall system setups for peak performance.

Multi-objective optimization has become essential for balancing competing design requirements such as power generation, structural integrity, and cost-effectiveness. A major goal is to reduce the cost of energy, which led to the development of second-generation design tools focused on that outcome [47]. These tools evaluate long term fatigue using time domain aeroelastic simulations and apply detailed cost models that connect design loads with manufacturing expenses.

The introduction of artificial intelligence and machine learning has significantly advanced optimization methods. By combining neural networks with genetic algorithms, engineers can identify optimal air foil shapes across varying angles of attack. To reduce computational demands, results are refined using neural network based approximations [48]. These techniques allow for fast assessment of design options without sacrificing the accuracy of performance predictions.

1.4.2.4 Advanced Control Systems and Performance Enhancement

Modern wind turbines incorporate sophisticated control systems that optimize performance across varying operational conditions. Active yaw control is used for implementing wake steering to optimize the balance between wind farm power production and loads [49].

Pitch control systems have begun to incorporate adaptive algorithms that respond to real time wind conditions and structural loads. Advanced fuzzy logic controllers enable smart, automated control of yaw movement, taking into account both wind velocity and acceptable yaw error correlation in order to maintain optimal turbine performance under varying conditions. [50]. These intelligent control systems enable wind turbines to maintain power output close to nominal values while preserving mechanical systems from unnecessary wear.

Wake steering and wind farm optimization are now recognized as critical areas of investigation in wind energy research. Wind plant control strategies that optimize yaw settings of wind turbines for improved energy production of the whole wind plant by taking into account wake effects, demonstrate increased energy production with reduction of loads on turbines as an additional effect [51]. These control strategies represent the evolution from individual turbine optimization to system level performance enhancement.

1.4.2.5 Performance Optimization Through Scale and Design Integration

As wind turbines continue to grow in size and are deployed more widely, integrated approaches design optimization has had to evolve into a more integrated process that considers the interactions between aerodynamics, structures, and control systems. This expansion into larger and more varied installations introduces new scientific and engineering challenges, demanding deeper insight into atmospheric flow physics, material properties, system dynamics, and strategies for optimizing entire wind farm fleets [52].

Optimizing turbine placement within wind farms has grown more advanced, with new multi-stage strategies delivering higher annual energy output and faster computation times than earlier optimization methods [53]. These methods are especially important for designing and optimizing layouts in large offshore wind farms, this an area of growing relevance given Ireland's ambitious renewable energy goals. With plans underway for floating wind projects reaching capacities of up to 1 GW, and continued growth in the national wind energy sector, effective layout optimization is becoming economically vital to ensure strong returns on the significant capital investments involved in offshore development.

System-level optimization increasingly considers the entire turbine lifecycle, from manufacturing through operation to end of life management. Design optimization of wind turbine blades aims to compete with traditional power technologies by decreasing cost and increasing efficiency through the use of optimization techniques that minimize blade mass while meeting frequency and strength constraints [54]. This comprehensive approach to design optimization ensures that performance improvements translate into practical benefits throughout the turbine's operational life. This is particularly crucial in Ireland, where wind energy already supplies 33% of electricity and the industry is undergoing rapid growth, fuelled by major offshore development plans.

1.5 Wind Turbine End-of-Life Management

The renewable energy sector's growth has created new waste streams, particularly from wind turbine blades reaching end-of-life. These composite structures present unique recycling challenges due to their thermoset matrix and fibre reinforcement. As the first generation of commercial wind turbines, installed in the 1990s and early 2000s, approaches the end of their 20–25-year operational lifetime, the industry faces unprecedented challenges in managing substantial volumes of composite waste materials [55]. The majority of blade decommission studies in life cycle assessments assume either landfilling or incineration of used wind blades, with most LCA studies not including end of life management of blades at all [56].

The scale of the challenge is significant. Between 7.7 and 23.1 million tonnes of wind turbine blade waste could be generated in China by 2050 [57]. In Europe, approximately 350,000 tonnes of end of life wind turbine blades are expected to be decommissioned by 2030 [58]. These projections highlight the urgent need for sustainable end-of-life management strategies

that can handle the increasing volume of decommissioned blade materials while maintaining the environmental benefits associated with wind energy generation.

Wind turbine end-of-life management strategies can be categorized into "reactive" approaches for dealing with existing aging turbines and "proactive" strategies designed to ensure recyclability of new generations of wind turbines [56]. Reactive options include improved maintenance and repair, health monitoring, damage reporting and identification, repair procedures, and quality control. However, even with life extension efforts, turbines eventually require recycling or disposal, making the development of effective waste management technologies critically important for the industry's long-term sustainability.

Figure 4 .Various approaches for the extension of lifetime of wind turbine blades. Recreated from [56].

1.5.1 Wind Turbine Blade Composition and Structure

Modern wind turbine blades have become sophisticated composite structures that have been engineered to operate for decades while withstanding challenging environmental conditions. Glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) has served as the most common choice of composite

material for wind turbine blades. This is because it is light weight and has excellent mechanical properties [59]. The typical blade structure consists of multiple components, including spar caps, shear webs, shell structures, and leading/trailing edge reinforcements, each of which are optimized for specific load bearing requirements.

The composite materials used in blade construction are mainly comprised of glass fibre reinforcement which is embedded in thermoset polymer matrices, this is typically epoxy or polyester resins. Glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRPs) were selected in the early wind turbine days because of good material availability and well documented processing technology [60]. As blade sizes have increased, carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRPs) are now replacing GFRPs in large turbine blades due to their enhanced stiffness and strength properties. This evolution toward hybrid designs, combining CFRP spar caps with GFRP skins, has become the current industry standard for large scale applications.

The structural complexity of modern blades extends beyond material selection to include sophisticated layup configurations and manufacturing processes. Unidirectional fibres are placed along the spar axis to provide bending stiffness, while $\pm 45^\circ$ layers in the skins and webs are used to resist twisting and shearing [61]. Advanced manufacturing techniques, including resin transfer moulding and vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding, ensure consistent quality and dimensional accuracy for these large structures.

The adhesive systems and core materials used in blade construction add further complexity to recycling challenges. Structural adhesives bond various blade sections together, while foam or balsa wood cores provide lightweight structural support in a sandwich configuration. The wider short life cycle of fibre reinforced polymer composites, especially in wind turbine blades, raises questions about their end of life scenarios [56]. While these multi material systems are essential for blade performance, they create significant challenges for end of life material separation and recovery.

1.5.2 Current Disposal Methods and Environmental Impact

Despite the environmental benefits of wind energy, the disposal of end of life turbine blades has become a significant environmental challenge. Scrap and end-of-life CFRP and GFRP components are currently destined mainly for landfill or incineration, as these are the processes used by traditional waste disposal businesses [62]. The conventional approach to blade disposal

as illustrated in figure 5 highlights that while recycling systems work well for metals and traditional materials, they simply cannot handle complex composite structures.

Figure 5. Discarded Wind Turbine Blades cover 30 acres [63].

Landfilling represents the most common disposal method for decommissioned wind turbine blades globally. With an estimated 800,000 tonnes of turbine blades entering landfill annually, this approach presents multiple environmental concerns [64]. Landfilling necessitates a considerable amount of land and does not allow for the recovery of composites' embodied energy. The non-biodegradable nature of fibre reinforced composites means that landfilled blade materials will remain in the environment for many decades, this is a permanent loss of valuable resources and energy that is embodied in their manufacture.

The environmental impact of landfilling extends beyond space utilization. In the United States, turbine blades may be disposed of in landfills, adding a new solid waste stream to the material already being landfilled [55]. Regional landfill capacity constraints could become increasingly problematic as blade waste volumes grow. While composite materials are generally considered inert, concerns exist regarding potential long term environmental impacts from degradation products, particularly from epoxy resins and their additives.

Incineration is an alternative disposal approach that can recover energy content from composite materials and reduce landfill requirements. Incineration, such as burning composite scrap in cement kilns, not only recovers the embodied energy, but also incorporates incombustible elements like glass fibres and mineral fillers into cement manufacture [62]. This approach presents significant environmental concerns. Incineration of the matrix components releases various harmful byproducts, such as calcium oxide formed from calcium carbonate, along with boron and other glass-derived oxides. The smoke or fumes from this should be considered carcinogenic and avoided through ventilation [62].

Austria, Finland, Germany, and the Netherlands already have a landfill ban in place for composite waste materials [65]. China has banned the landfilling of solid turbine waste, making mechanical recycling followed by landfill of residual materials non-viable[66]. The European Union's Waste Framework Directive reinforces this trend by specifying that landfilling should be a last resort after prevention, preparation for re-use, recycling and recovery[56].

Life cycle assessments of wind energy systems reveal that despite disposal challenges, the environmental benefits of wind energy significantly outweigh end of life impacts. The positive environmental impact of wind turbines outweighs the negative, in terms of the role they play in reaching a net zero future [67]. Turbine blades are responsible for providing between 120,000 and 180,000 hours of electricity generation in their lifespans, making them a crucial part of the energy transition. Addressing end of life challenges remains essential for maintaining the industry's environmental credibility and regulatory compliance.

1.5.3 Emerging Recycling Technologies

The development of advanced recycling technologies for wind turbine blades has become a critical research and commercial priority. This is driven by increasing waste volumes and regulatory pressures [56]. Studies on the application of wind turbine blade waste materials in civil engineering have shown an increasing trend as is highlighted by the growing number of new publications in this field [62]. Three primary methods have emerged as commercially viable solutions ,mechanical recycling, thermal recycling , and chemical recycling [68]

Mechanical recycling represents the most technologically advanced and well-established method for processing blade waste. Mechanical recycling is a cost efficient process with a low carbon footprint. This method involves crushing, grinding, and sieving treatments to separate epoxy resin and glass fibres. Mechanical recycling, used to facilitate coprocessing, is regarded

as the most practical solution for treating end of life blade waste. This recommendation is based on a comprehensive assessment of available methods and their respective technology readiness levels, with mechanical recycling standing out for its proven commercial scalability [62]. The recovered materials experience some degradation in mechanical properties, but still find applications in concrete reinforcement, construction materials, and lower-performance composite applications.

Thermal recycling technologies, particularly pyrolysis, have shown significant promise for material recovery from composite waste. Pyrolysis process breaks down old composite materials, such as glass fibre reinforced epoxy resin composites, using special catalysts to separate valuable components for reuse and recycle old composite materials into useful energy [69]. Pyrolysis process is carried out by heating the material between 450 and 700°C in the absence of oxygen, converting the polymer matrix into gas, oil and char, while the fibres remain inert and can be later recovered [56]. Pyrolysis has its drawbacks, with the risk of char formation on the final fibre surface being the most difficult, this can cause mechanical properties of the recovered fibres to decrease significantly.

Chemical recycling through solvolysis recovers clean, intact fibres and reuses resin, and this could close the fibre reinforced resin composites loop [70]. Chemical recycling is one of the most promising recycling methods due to more clean and higher strength fibres and due to lower temperatures versus pyrolysis. The process typically operates at temperatures below 200°C, this is a significant reduction in energy requirements compared to thermal methods while achieving superior material recovery rates.

Recent comparative assessments have evaluated the environmental performance of different recycling approaches. Blade recycling via solvolysis is the most circular solution [71]. Solvolysis has the most positive impacts on the environment, mainly because of the potential to produce recovered carbon fibre, while transitioning to renewable electricity in recycling processes revealed a potential reduction in environmental impact by around 33-85% depending on end of life treatment [72].

The commercial use of these technologies is advancing rapidly. Carbon Rivers' recycling uses pyrolysis to convert organic products back into raw hydrocarbon products called syngas and pyrolysis oil, which can be used for energy production, while separated recycled glass fibre can be collected for direct reuse in manufacturing new products [73]. The REWIND Project aims to develop critical technologies for dismantling wind turbine blades and implement new

methods for composites repurposing and recycling to enhance their circularity, representing coordinated European efforts to commercialize advanced recycling technologies. Figure 6 demonstrates commercial applications of these recycling technologies, showing products made from recycled wind turbine blade materials [56].

Figure 6. Products made from recycled wind turbine blade materials by Global Fiberglass Solutions, including EcoPoly pellets, EcoPoly panels, and roadway applications demonstrating commercial applications of mechanical recycling technologies (Adapted from [56], Figure 6).

The Technology Readiness Levels for different recycling approaches vary significantly. Mechanical recycling demonstrates the highest TRL rating of 9, indicating commercial maturity, while maintaining 78% and 50% retained tensile strength for glass fibre and carbon fibre respectively. Pyrolysis operates at TRL 7 with moderate retained tensile strengths (52% for GF, 78% for CF), while chemical recycling methods such as solvolysis operate at lower TRL levels (5/6) but offer superior material recovery potential with 58% and 95% retained tensile strength for GF and CF respectively. Co-processing techniques achieve TRL ratings of 8-9, making them among the most commercially viable approaches alongside mechanical recycling. Existing recycling processes such as pyrolysis and solvolysis are the most likely to provide a commercially viable recycling route for this type of waste, with continued

development expected to improve both economic viability and environmental performance [62]

Table 1. Technology Readiness Level (TRL) comparison for different wind turbine blade recycling technologies. Recreated from [62].

Recycling Methods	TRL	Waste Management Score	Predicted needed investment	Machining options	Retained TS GF(%) CF(%)	
Mechanical	9	Low	Low	GF+CF	78	50
Co-Processing	8-9	Middle	Low/Middle	GF	-	-
Pyrolysis	7	High	Low/Middle	GF+CF	52	78
Microwave Pyrolysis	4	Middle/High	High	GF+CF	52	80
Fluidized bed	4/5	Middle/High	Middle	GF+CF	50	75
Solvolyis	5/6	High	High	GF+CF	58	95

1.6 Potential to Repurpose Waste into New Enhanced Products

The transition from linear to circular economy models has opened exciting new opportunities to turn industrial waste into valuable resources. The concept of "waste-to-resource" represents a fundamental shift in how industries approach material management, particularly for polymer waste streams that traditionally end up in landfills or incineration facilities. This approach supports sustainability and helps meet the demand for affordable materials with specific qualities [74]. The development of enhanced products from recycled materials requires a comprehensive understanding of material degradation mechanisms, compatibilization strategies, and how processing will affect the final product performance.

1.6.1 Composite Material Recycling and Enhancement

Advanced composite recycling technologies are expanding the potential for creating enhanced products from wind turbine blade waste and other industrial composites. The recovery of fibres and matrix materials through mechanical, thermal, and chemical recycling processes provides opportunities for developing new composite formulations with improved performance characteristics compared to conventional recycled materials [75]. Recently the focus in composite recycling have been on maintaining fibre integrity while enabling matrix

reprocessing, this results in recycled composite materials that can achieve mechanical properties close to the properties of virgin materials.

Mechanical recycling of composite materials typically involves size reduction, separation, and reprocessing steps that can be optimized to preserve fibre length and orientation. The recovered short fibres can be incorporated into new composite systems as reinforcement materials, providing enhanced strength and stiffness compared to unreinforced polymer matrices [76]. Glass fibre recovered from wind turbine blades through mechanical recycling has shown potential for reinforcing polyolefin matrices, creating hybrid materials that combine the cost effectiveness of recycled content with improved mechanical performance.

Thermal recycling approaches, particularly optimized pyrolysis processes, have enabled the recovery of clean fibres with minimal surface contamination. The pyrolysis process at optimized temperatures (450-500°C) can effectively decompose the polymer matrix while preserving fibre integrity, achieving up to 90% retention of mechanical properties of original fibre [77]. These recovered fibres can be incorporated into new polymer systems, including polyolefin blends, to create enhanced composite materials with superior performance compared to conventional recycled products.

Chemical recycling through solvolysis is becoming popular due to its ability to recover clean, high-quality fibres that can be used to enhance composite materials. The process operates at lower temperatures than pyrolysis but can achieve superior material recovery rates, making it attractive for producing high performance recycled composites [78].

1.6.2 Polyolefin Recycling: Challenges and Current Practices

A major challenge in recycling polyolefin is the difficulty in blending different types of polymers, which don't naturally mix well together. This, combined with the wear and tear materials go through during repeated processing, often results in lower quality recycled outputs. The similar densities and chemical properties of polyethylene and polypropylene make physical separation difficult, while their thermodynamic incompatibility results in poor mechanical properties when blended together [74]. Mechanical recycling of polyolefins typically involves high processing temperatures that can compromise structural stability and mechanical strength of the recycled products.

Current mechanical recycling practices for polyolefins demonstrate both limitations and opportunities for enhancement. Despite mechanical recycling's prevalence in polyolefin waste processing, the process faces challenges including thermal degradation, contamination from additives, and property deterioration with each recycling cycle [79]. Post consumer recycle (PCR) often has reduced mechanical properties in comparison to virgin materials, this is due to chain scission, oxidation, and contamination from previous applications.

Advanced chemical recycling technologies provide viable routes for enhancing the value of polyolefin waste streams. Temperature gradient thermolysis has shown potential for converting waste polyolefins into valuable chemicals, with economic studies indicating feasibility for scaling up to industrial levels [74]. This process breaks long chain polyolefin molecules into shorter wax like compounds that can be used in the production of detergents and other chemicals, offering an alternative to traditional mechanical recycling.

The development of catalytic systems for polyolefin degradation has opened new pathways for creating enhanced products from waste streams. Precise activation of C-C bonds through catalytic processes enables selective conversion of polyolefin waste into specific chemical products, allowing better control over product quality and composition compared to conventional thermal processing [79]. These catalytic approaches can potentially address the problem of limited product selectivity in non-catalytic pyrolysis, while still remaining economically viable.

1.6.3 Polymer Blend Compatibilization

Effective compatibilization techniques are essential for creating enhanced products from mixed polymer waste streams. The main challenge is the thermodynamic incompatibility between different polymer types. This often results in poor interfacial adhesion and inferior mechanical properties in uncompatibilized blends. Compatibilizers function by reducing interfacial tension, improving dispersion of minor components, and enhancing adhesion between polymer phases [80].

Reactive compatibilization through maleic anhydride grafting has been seen to be particularly effective for polyolefin blends. Maleic anhydride-grafted polymers can form graft copolymers at polymer interfaces, creating strong interfacial bonds that significantly improve blend properties. The anhydride groups react with functional groups present in other polymers or additives, forming chemical bridges that enhance compatibility and mechanical performance

[81]. This approach has been successfully applied to PP/PE blends, significantly improving tensile strength and impact properties compared to uncompatibilized blends.

Non-reactive compatibilization using block or graft copolymers provides an alternative approach for improving blend properties. By settling at polymer interfaces, compatibilizers reduce interfacial tension and preserve blend structure throughout processing, minimizing phase separation. Recent advances in synthetic chemistry have enabled access to precision architectures that can significantly outperform traditional diblock compatibilizers [82]. Multiblock copolymer compatibilizers with four or more blocks have demonstrated superior performance compared to conventional diblock systems.

Modern compatibilization approaches are increasingly centred on generating compatibilizing agents directly within the melt phase during processing. This method uses reactive groups present in the polymers to drive reactions with complementary functionalized additives, creating compatibilizing copolymers during the blending process. The rate of compatibilizer formation must be balanced with the rate of droplet breakup during processing to optimize blend morphology and properties [83]. This dynamic approach allows for real time optimization of blend properties based on processing conditions.

1.6.4 Effects of Repeated Processing on Polymer Properties

Repeated processing cycles significantly impact polymer properties through various degradation mechanisms that must be understood for effective waste valorisation. Temperature, mechanical stress, and oxygen exposure during processing promote thermal, thermo-mechanical, and thermal oxidative degradation pathways that can compromise material performance [84]. Understanding these degradation mechanisms is crucial for developing strategies to minimize property loss during recycling and reprocessing operations.

Repeated processing primarily impacts polymer properties through thermal degradation. Initial degradation of polyolefins is driven primarily by chain scission, with elevated oxygen levels promoting a shift toward long chain branching development. The balance between these mechanisms determines the final properties of reprocessed materials, with chain scission typically reducing molecular weight and mechanical strength while branching can increase melt viscosity and processing difficulties [85].

Molecular weight reduction is a consistent result of repeated processing, with studies showing progressive decreases in average molecular weight with each processing cycle. For example, polylactic acid (PLA) demonstrates molecular weight reduction from 175,888 g/mol to 90,021 g/mol after five recycling cycles, resulting in corresponding decreases in mechanical properties [86]. This molecular weight degradation occurs through thermally activated chain scission mechanisms that are accelerated by elevated processing temperatures and extended residence times. Table 2 illustrates the typical changes in mechanical properties observed across different polymers after recycling processes [87]

These morphological changes influence mechanical properties, with increased crystallinity potentially increasing brittleness and contributing to mechanical strength degradation [86]

Table 2 . Changes in mechanical properties of the polymers after the recycling process. **a = virgin polymer** (1 extrusion cycle) **b = recycled polymer** (5 extrusion cycles). Recreated from [88]

Polymer	Extrusion Cycles	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Impact Strength (kJ/m²)
PLA		77.7 ±		
	1	7.4 ^a	2.5 ± 0.7 ^a	7.7 ± 0.2 ^a
	5	75.0 ±	2.2 ± 0.1 ^b	7.0 ± 0.1 ^b
Bioflex		3.4 ^b		
	1	9.0 ±	0.3 ± 0.0 ^a	9.1 ± 0.5 ^a
	5	8.2 ±	0.2 ± 0.0 ^b	0.2 ± 0.0 ^b
Solanyl		0.2 ^b		
	1	15.1 ±	1.4 ± 0.0 ^a	2.1 ± 0.4 ^a
	5	15.2 ±	1.3 ± 0.1 ^b	2.1 ± 0.3 ^a
PHBV		0.1 ^a		
	1	47.4 ±	3.2 ± 0.3 ^a	3.7 ± 0.1 ^a
	5	46.5 ±	2.7 ± 0.2 ^b	2.6 ± 0.1 ^b
		4.9 ^b		

Processing atmosphere significantly influences degradation mechanisms and the extent of property loss during repeated processing. Inert atmospheres (nitrogen, argon, CO₂) primarily promote thermal degradation through chain scission, while oxygen-containing atmospheres accelerate thermal-oxidative processes that can lead to crosslinking and more severe property degradation. The ability to control processing atmosphere provides opportunities for minimizing degradation and preserving valuable material properties during recycling operations [87]. Figure 7 demonstrates these effects specifically for HDPE, showing progressive changes in melt flow index during extensive recycling cycles [89]

Figure 7. Melt flow index changes during extensive HDPE recycling [89]

2. Methods

2.1 Materials

Mixed Polyethylene Waste (MPE) was supplied by Plaswire Limited (Portadown Rd, Lurgan, Armagh, Northern Ireland) and used as received. The MPE represents industrial waste that would typically be destined for landfill due to contamination and mixed polymer composition, making it unsuitable for conventional recycling processes.

Shredded Wind Turbine Blade material (WTB) was supplied by Plaswire Limited and used as received. The WTB material comprised a combination of thermoset polymer matrix and glass fibres of varying lengths, representing typical end-of-life wind turbine blade waste that would otherwise be landfilled or incinerated.

2.2 Blend Preparation and Compounding

2.2.1 Blend Formulations

Various weight percentage blends of industrial olefins and industrial composites were prepared to investigate the effect of composition on mechanical properties and identify optimum composition ranges for different application requirements. The formulations processed in this study included WTB loadings of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 60% by weight incorporated into the MPE matrix. A control sample containing 0% WTB (pure MPE) was also prepared for comparison. The materials were weighed separately, placed into sealed polyethylene bags and manually blended for 10 minutes to ensure a homogenous mixture.

Table 3. Blend compositions produced in this study.

Sample	MPE	WTB
	(wt.	(Wt.
	%)	%)
1	100	0
2	90	10
3	80	20
4	70	30
5	60	40
6	40	60

2.2.2 Compounding Process

The Extrusion parameters used to carry out this trial are listed in Table 3. The mixed blends were processed in a Leistritz 27 mm co-rotating twin screw extruder (*Leistritz Extrusionstechnik GmbH, Nürnberg, Germany*) with a 40 L/D ratio with the rotational speed of the screws kept constant at 100 RPM with a material feed rate of 10 kg/hr. The resultant extrudate was air-cooled prior to pelletizing to a pellet length of 1.0 mm.

Table 4. Extrusion parameters utilised for composite manufacture.

Zone	Temperature (°C)
Barrel Zone 1	100
Barrel Zone 2	100
Barrel Zone 3	100
Barrel Zone 4	160
Barrel Zone 5	160
Barrel Zone 6	180
Barrel Zone 7	180
Barrel Zone 8	180
Flange	180
Die	180

2.3 Sample Preparation

Test specimens were manufactured using injection moulding to produce standardized samples for mechanical characterization. The injection moulding process was carried out using a DEMAG injection moulding machine with processing parameters detailed in Table 4.

Table 5. Injection moulding parameters used for composite production.

Parameter	Unit	Setting
Barrel Zone 1 Temperature	°C	160
Barrel Zone 2 Temperature	°C	170
Barrel Zone 3 Temperature	°C	180
Nozzle Temperature	°C	190
Mould Temperature	°C	30

Standard test specimens were produced for tensile testing (dog-bone shaped), flexural testing (rectangular bars), and impact testing (rectangular bars) to enable comprehensive mechanical characterization of all blend formulations.

Figure 8. Moulded composite tensile bars and impact/flexural test specimens. (L-R) 0% WTB, 10% WTB, 20% WTB, 30% WTB, 40% WTB & 60% WTB.

2.4 Mechanical Testing

2.4.1 Tensile Testing

Tensile testing was performed using a Zwick Roell tensile tester (Ulm, Germany). The samples (size Lx12.8mm x 3mm) were fixed using 2 screw side action tensile grips. Each formulation was tested using six samples in a 2.5kN load cell at 50mm.min⁻¹ with a 0.5N preload and 100mm gauge length. The percentage of elongation was calculated using Equation 1.

$$\% \text{ Elongation} = \left(\frac{\text{Deflection at break (mm)}}{\text{Gauge length (mm)}} \right) \times 100$$

Equation1.

2.4.2 Flexural Testing

Flexural testing was conducted on Lloyd LRX Tensometer (*Hampshire, United Kingdom*) after conditioning for a minimum of 24 hours at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The Tensometer was fitted with a 2.5kN loadcell and 3-point bending jig. Experimental settings were in accordance with ISO 178. Six replicates were placed centrally across two rollers with a span of 96mm and tested at a speed of 2mm/min.

2.4.3 Impact Testing

Impact testing was carried out on a Zwick Roell CEAST 6545 (*Ulm, Germany*). Six specimens were tested for each formulation using a 4J interchangeable pendulum. Samples (size L x 12.55mm x 6mm) were placed horizontally and supported by 2 anvils. Each test was initiated manually by pressing operator buttons on the left and right side of the machine simultaneously. Energy absorption values were displayed on the machine after each test and manually recorded.

3. Results

3.1 Impact Strength

The results of impact testing are displayed in Table 5 and Figure 9

Table 6. Mean Impact values of MPE/WTB composites. Results are shown \pm standard deviation.

Sample	Impact Strength (J)
0%	DNB
10%	DNB
20%	5.49 \pm 0.011
30%	3.74 \pm 0.413
40%	1.49 \pm 0.108
60%	0.72 \pm 0.021

Figure 9. Impact strength of tested composite samples. Samples that absorbed >5.5 J did not break under testing.

The impact testing results provide the most significant evidence of mechanical property degradation with increasing WTB content. Pure MPE and 10% WTB composites both exhibit impact energies exceeding 5.5J, causing specimens to not break under the 4J testing conditions. This impact resistance indicates excellent energy absorption capability and ductile failure behaviour.

A notable transition occurs between 10% and 20% WTB loading, where impact strength drops to $5.49 \pm 0.011\text{J}$. Beyond this transition point, impact strength continues to decline linearly: $3.74 \pm 0.413\text{J}$ at 30% WTB, $1.49 \pm 0.108\text{J}$ at 40% WTB, and finally $0.72 \pm 0.021\text{J}$ at 60% WTB loading.

3.2 Tensile Properties

The results of the tensile testing are displayed in Figure 10 and the ascertained data tabulated in Table 6.

Table 7. Tensile properties. UTS – Ultimate tensile strength.

Sample	Maximum Load (kN)	Load at break (kN)	UTS (Mpa)	Elongation (%)	Strain (%)
0%WTB	1.048±0.009	0.209±0.002	5.479±0.041	11.859±0.404	26.134±0.779
10%WTB	1.056±0.011	0.211±0.002	5.542±0.068	11.165±0.321	16.005±1.873
20%WTB	1.0101±0.028	0.202±0.006	5.393±0.245	8.054±0.485	9.295±0.291
30%WTB	0.973±0.022	0.195±0.004	5.155±0.113	6.429±0.333	7.045±0.281
40%WTB	0.819±0.034	0.164±0.007	4.326±0.182	3.094±0.289	3.348±0.271
60%WTB	0.739±0.027	0.148±0.005	3.907±0.146	1.189±0.074	1.421±0.082

Figure 10. Mean values of Youngs modulus (blue) and ultimate tensile strength (red).

The tensile testing results reveal several critical trends that define the mechanical behaviour of the composites. Ultimate tensile strength decreases progressively from 5.479 ± 0.041 MPa for pure MPE to 3.907 ± 0.146 MPa at 60% WTB loading, representing a 29% reduction in load-bearing capacity. This decline is accompanied by an even more dramatic reduction in ductility, with elongation at break decreasing from $11.859 \pm 0.404\%$ to $1.189 \pm 0.074\%$, a 90% loss in extensibility.

The strain at break data reinforces this trend, showing a reduction from $26.134 \pm 0.779\%$ for pure MPE to just $1.421 \pm 0.082\%$ at maximum WTB loading. This transformation from a ductile to brittle material behaviour represents one of the most significant findings of this research, indicating that WTB incorporation fundamentally alters the failure mechanisms of the composite system.

Young's modulus results present an interesting contrast to the strength and ductility trends. The modulus increases systematically from approximately 1000 MPa for pure MPE to 2150 MPa at 60% WTB loading, representing a 115% increase in stiffness. This stiffening effect indicates that the glass fibres within the WTB material are contributing to composite rigidity, even though overall mechanical performance is compromised.

3.3 Flexural Properties

The flexural testing results reveal a different trend compared to tensile and impact properties, with systematic improvements observed across all measured parameters as WTB content increases. The 3-point bending test demonstrates that while WTB incorporation compromises tensile strength and impact resistance, it provides significant enhancement to flexural performance characteristics.

Table 8. Flexural properties of MPE/WTB composites.

Sample	Max Bending Stress (MPa)	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Max Load (N)	Elastic Strength (MPa)
0% WTB	8.75 ± 0.31	455 ± 68	32.8 ± 1.2	1.417 ± 0.263
10% WTB	10.81 ± 0.15	616 ± 107	39.8 ± 0.3	1.528 ± 0.572
20% WTB	12.64 ± 0.17	736 ± 124	46.2 ± 0.2	2.333 ± 0.768
30% WTB	14.06 ± 0.15	836 ± 32	51.8 ± 0.5	2.486 ± 0.324
40% WTB	17.29 ± 0.31	1139 ± 68	64.5 ± 0.6	2.562 ± 0.726
60% WTB	19.59 ± 0.45	1536 ± 43	73.6 ± 1.2	3.443 ± 0.452

Figure 11 .Flexural Stress Properties vs WTB Content

The Maximum bending stress displays consistent progressive improvement with increasing WTB content, rising from 8.75 ± 0.31 MPa for pure MPE to 19.59 ± 0.45 MPa at 60% WTB loading. This represents a substantial 123.8% increase in flexural strength. Indicating the glass fibres within the WTB material provide effective reinforcement under bending loads.

Figure 12. Young's Modulus and Maximum Load vs WTB Content

The Young's modulus values from flexural testing show exceptional improvement, increasing from 455 ± 68 MPa to 1538 ± 43 MPa, representing a 237.3% improvement. This dramatic

stiffening effect is consistent with the tensile modulus trends observed in section 3.2, confirming that WTB incorporation significantly enhances composite rigidity across different loading modes.

Maximum load capacity follows a similar upward trend, increasing from $32.8 \pm 1.2\text{N}$ to $73.6 \pm 1.2\text{N}$, a 124.6% improvement that demonstrates the superior load bearing capacity of high WTB content composites under flexural loading conditions. The elastic strength shows improvements increasing from 143.0% from $1.417 \pm 0.263\text{MPa}$ to $3.443 \pm 0.452\text{MPa}$.

This consistently low standard deviation across all WTB loadings indicates excellent repeatability in the flexural testing results, this suggests that the manufacturing process achieved adequate dispersion and consistent material properties. The progressive enhancement of flexural properties indicates that this is directly proportional to WTB content, contrasting with the degradation observed in tensile strength and impact resistance.

3.4 Surface Morphology

The visual examination of the injection moulded specimens, as shown in Figure 8, displays significant morphological changes in the composite materials as WTB content increases. The progression from pure MPE (0% WTB) to the highest loading (60% WTB) demonstrates clear evidence of successful incorporation of the wind turbine blade material, with observable effects on surface characteristics and overall specimen appearance.

3.4.1 Visual Appearance and Colour Characteristics

Visual examination of the injection moulded specimens reveals that all formulations are dark in colour indicating that the mixed polyethylene waste (MPE) matrix itself contributes significantly to the overall coloration. The specimens across the entire WTB loading range from 0% to 60% show consistently dark coloration, which reflects the industrial waste nature of the base MPE material.

While systematic colour changes with increasing WTB content are not readily apparent due to the inherently dark nature of the MPE matrix, the successful incorporation of WTB material is evidenced through other morphological features. The consistent dark appearance across all

formulations suggests that the industrial waste polyethylene matrix dominates the visual characteristics rather than the WTB additions creating noticeable colour progression.

3.4.2 Surface Texture and Finish

Visual inspection of the moulded specimens reveals changes in surface texture that correlate with WTB content. The pure MPE specimens display smooth, glossy surfaces typical of well-processed polyolefin materials. However, as WTB loading increases, the surface finish becomes progressively more matte and textured.

At higher WTB loadings (40% and 60%), the surface shows increased roughness that can be attributed to the presence of glass fibres at or near the surface. This surface roughening is consistent with the heterogeneous nature of the composite material and indicates that the rigid inclusions are affecting the flow characteristics during injection moulding.

3.4.3 Fiber Visibility and Distribution

In specimens with higher WTB content, individual glass fibres become visible at the surface, particularly in the 40% and 60% WTB samples. The visibility of fibres at the surface suggests that the injection moulding process has oriented some fibres parallel to the flow direction, which is typical behaviour for short fibre reinforced composites.

The distribution of visible fibres appears relatively uniform across the specimen surfaces, indicating that the twin screw extrusion process achieved reasonable dispersion of the WTB material. However, some localized variations in fibre density are observable, suggesting that complete homogenization was not achieved under the current processing conditions.

3.4.4 Processing-Related Surface Features

The injection moulded specimens exhibit typical features associated with thermoplastic processing, including gate marks and flow lines. However, these features become more pronounced as WTB content increases, indicating that the presence of solid inclusions affects the flow behaviour of the polymer melt during moulding.

At higher WTB loadings, some specimens show evidence of fibre orientation effects, with subtle flow patterns visible on the surface that correspond to the injection moulding flow

direction. These orientation effects are consistent with the mechanical property anisotropy typically observed in short fibre reinforced composites.

3.4.5 Surface Defects and Discontinuities

Higher WTB loadings show increased surface irregularities, including small voids and surface discontinuities that may be attributed to poor interfacial adhesion between the WTB components and the polyolefin matrix. These surface defects become more prevalent as loading increases, particularly at 60% WTB where some specimens exhibit visible surface porosity.

The presence of these surface defects correlates with the observed mechanical property degradation, suggesting that the poor interfacial bonding extends throughout the composite structure rather than being limited to internal interfaces.

4. Discussion

4.1 Mechanical Properties

The mechanical characterization of MPE/WTB composites reveals systematic and significant changes in material behaviour as wind turbine blade content increases. The comprehensive testing program, encompassing tensile, impact, and stiffness measurements, demonstrates the complex relationship between waste material incorporation and composite performance.

4.1.1 Overall Mechanical Performance Trends

The mechanical testing results show a consistent pattern of property degradation with increasing WTB content across all testing methods. This systematic decline indicates that while WTB incorporation is technically feasible, significant challenges exist in maintaining mechanical performance. The results suggest that current processing conditions and material combinations are not optimized for mechanical property retention.

4.1.2 Tensile Properties Analysis

The tensile testing results reveal several critical trends that define the mechanical behaviour of the composites. Ultimate tensile strength decreases progressively from 5.479 ± 0.041 MPa for pure MPE to 3.907 ± 0.146 MPa at 60% WTB loading, representing a 29% reduction in load-bearing capacity. This decline is consistent with the work by Shojaeiarani et al. [88] who reported similar strength reductions in recycled biopolymers due to reprocessing operations. Both studies demonstrate that processing waste materials under thermal conditions promotes common degradation mechanisms including thermal degradation, chain scission, and the introduction of interfacial defects. In Shojaeiarani's work, repeated processing cycles of biopolymers created stress concentration sites and molecular level damage, while in this study, the incorporation of WTB waste into the MPE matrix introduces similar weakening mechanisms through poor interfacial bonding between dissimilar materials and the creation of rigid inclusions that act as stress concentrators. The parallel findings confirm that waste processing inherently introduces microstructural defects that compromise load bearing capacity, though the magnitude varies depending on the specific polymer system and processing conditions. This decline is accompanied by an even more dramatic reduction in ductility, with elongation at break decreasing from $11.859 \pm 0.404\%$ to $1.189 \pm 0.074\%$, a 90% loss in extensibility.

The strain at break data reinforces this trend, showing a reduction from $26.134 \pm 0.779\%$ for pure MPE to just $1.421 \pm 0.082\%$ at maximum WTB loading. This transformation from a ductile to brittle material behaviour represents one of the most significant findings of this research, indicating that WTB incorporation fundamentally alters the failure mechanisms of the composite system. This finding is consistent with work by Junaedi et al. [90] who identified similar ductile-to-brittle transitions in short carbon fibre reinforced polypropylene composites. Both studies demonstrate that the introduction of rigid inclusions into ductile polymer matrices promotes a shift from matrix-dominated failure to interface-dominated failure mechanisms. In Junaedi's work, short carbon fibres created stress concentration sites at the fibre-matrix interface, leading to premature crack initiation and brittle fracture behaviour. Similarly, in the present study, WTB particles act as rigid inclusions that constrain matrix deformation and create interfacial stress concentrations due to poor bonding with the MPE matrix. The ductile-to-brittle transition occurs because the polymer matrix can no longer undergo extensive plastic deformation before failure, as cracks preferentially initiate and propagate along the weak particle-matrix interfaces rather than through the ductile matrix material. This fundamental change in failure mechanism from energy-absorbing matrix deformation to low-energy interfacial fracture explains the dramatic reduction in impact resistance and elongation at break observed in both studies when rigid reinforcements are introduced into ductile polymer systems.

Young's modulus results present an interesting contrast to the strength and ductility trends. The modulus increases systematically from approximately 1000 MPa for pure MPE to 2150 MPa at 60% WTB loading, representing a 115% increase in stiffness. This stiffening effect indicates that the glass fibres within the WTB material are contributing to composite rigidity, even though overall mechanical performance is compromised [91,92].

4.1.3 Impact Resistance Behaviour

The impact testing results provide the most dramatic evidence of mechanical property degradation. Pure MPE and 10% WTB composites both exhibit impact energies exceeding 5.5J, causing specimens to not break under the 4J testing conditions. This exceptional impact resistance indicates excellent energy absorption capability and ductile failure behaviour.

A critical transition occurs between 10% and 20% WTB loading, where impact strength drops to $5.49 \pm 0.011\text{J}$. This threshold represents a fundamental change in failure mechanisms from

ductile energy absorption to brittle crack propagation, consistent with the ductile to brittle transition mechanisms described by Junaedi et al. [90] in fibre reinforced composites. Beyond this transition point, impact strength continues to decline linearly: $3.74 \pm 0.413\text{J}$ at 30% WTB, $1.49 \pm 0.108\text{J}$ at 40% WTB, and finally $0.72 \pm 0.021\text{J}$ at 60% WTB loading.

The linear relationship between WTB content and impact strength degradation suggests a systematic degradation mechanism rather than random material variations. This predictable behaviour indicates that impact resistance can be used as a reliable indicator of composite quality and processability.

4.1.4 Flexural Properties Analysis

The flexural testing results show a noticeable contrast compared to the trends observed in tensile and impact properties, revealing fundamental differences in how WTB incorporation affects composite behaviour under different loading modes. This distinctive response provides critical insights into the load transfer mechanisms and optimal applications for these waste-derived composites.

The improved performance under flexural loading is due to fundamental differences in stress distribution and failure behaviour between bending and tensile loading conditions. In flexural testing, the stress gradient from maximum at the outer fibre to zero at the neutral axis allows the glass fibres from WTB material to provide effective reinforcement in high stress regions while accommodating interfacial defects in lower stress areas. Under tensile loading, stress is distributed uniformly across the material, which increases the composite's sensitivity to interfacial bonding defects throughout the cross section.

This behaviour is consistent with classical composite mechanics theory, where short fibre reinforcement performs most effectively when fibres can bridge across tensile stress fields in bending applications [93]. The linear relationship between WTB content and flexural enhancement indicates that rigid fibre inclusions can provide beneficial mechanical reinforcement when the loading mode permits stress redistribution around poorly bonded interfaces [93,94].

These findings have significant implications for application selection. The superior flexural performance suggests these composites are particularly suited for bending-dominated applications such as structural panels, decking materials, or construction elements where

dimensional stability and flexural rigidity are prioritised over impact resistance. The contrast between flexural improvements and tensile/impact degradation confirms that material selection must consider the specific loading conditions and performance requirements of the intended application.

4.1.5 Mechanical Property Correlations

The inverse relationship between stiffness and toughness properties reveals a fundamental disconnect between the WTB reinforcement and the MPE matrix, indicating ineffective stress transfer mechanisms. The simultaneous increase in stiffness and decrease in strength and toughness indicates that the WTB components are acting as rigid inclusions rather than effective reinforcements. This behaviour is characteristic of poorly bonded particulate filled systems where stress transfer mechanisms are inefficient in comparison to work by Pukánszky [95] who demonstrated that poor interfacial interaction leads to reduced ultimate tensile properties in polymer composites.

The WTB loading of 10-20% represents a transition point where mechanical behaviour transitions from matrix dominated to inclusion dominated failure mechanisms. At loadings below this threshold, the continuous MPE matrix is able to redistribute stress around the WTB particles, maintaining some degree of ductility and impact resistance. Above this threshold, the density of stress concentration sites becomes sufficient to promote crack initiation and propagation through interfacial regions.

4.1.6 Implications for Material Design

The mechanical testing results highlight several key considerations for future material development. The dramatic loss of ductility and impact resistance limits the potential applications for these composites to non-structural uses where impact loading is minimal. The increased stiffness may be beneficial for applications requiring dimensional stability, but this advantage is offset by reduced toughness and fracture resistance.

4.1.7 Processing-Property Relationships

The findings for the mechanical properties show strong links between the production conditions and the composition of the material. The successful incorporation of up to 60%

WTB content indicates that the twin-screw extrusion process is capable of achieving basic mixing and dispersion. The mechanical property degradation shows that mixing alone is insufficient to achieve optimal composite performance.

The processing temperatures (160-180°C) appear adequate for thermoplastic flow while avoiding excessive thermal degradation. However, the mechanical results suggest that interfacial bonding remains poor despite adequate thermal energy for potential chemical interactions. This indicates that surface chemistry and compatibility, rather than processing temperature, represent the primary barriers to improved mechanical performance, as predicted by the interfacial bonding theory developed by Pukánszky [95].

5. Conclusion

5.1 Optimum Loading Determination

The research has successfully achieved its primary objective of determining optimum loading levels for recycling industrial waste into reusable products. The systematic processing of MPE/WTB composites across a wide range of compositions (0-60% WTB) demonstrates that large quantities of wind turbine blade waste can be diverted from landfills and incorporated into useful composite materials. This represents a significant contribution to sustainable materials development and circular economy principles.

The mechanical characterisation programme has provided valuable insights into the relationship between waste material incorporation and composite performance. The identification of critical thresholds, particularly the 10-20% WTB loading range where mechanical behaviour transitions, provides important guidance for future material optimisation. This knowledge allows informed decision to be made regarding appropriate applications and processing conditions for these recycled composites.

This research has demonstrated that certain properties can be enhanced through waste incorporation. The increase in Young's modulus from 1000 MPa to 2150 MPa with increasing WTB content shows that stiffness and dimensional stability can be significantly improved, making these materials suitable for applications requiring enhanced rigidity.

This research revealed that MPE/WTB composites can exhibit superior performance under flexural loading conditions, with results finding maximum bending stress increasing by 123.8% and flexural modulus improving by 237.3% at maximum WTB loading. This exceptional flexural performance demonstrates that these recycled composites can outperform virgin materials in bending dominated applications. This finding expands the potential market applications to include structural panels, decking materials, and construction elements where flexural rigidity and dimensional stability are prioritized over impact resistance.

The systematic mechanical characterization of MPE/WTB composites has quantified the trade-offs found through waste material incorporation and established optimum loading ranges for different applications. While ultimate tensile strength decreased by 29% and elongation at break was reduced by 90% at maximum WTB loading, the 115% increase in Young's modulus demonstrates that dimensional stability and stiffness can be enhanced. Based on these findings, loadings below 10% WTB are optimal for impact-critical applications, while 30-40% WTB loadings provide optimal performance for structural applications requiring enhanced flexural properties.

5.2 Industrial Waste Recovery Impact

This work addresses a critical environmental challenge by providing a practical solution for two major waste streams, mixed polyethylene industrial waste and end of life wind turbine blades[25]. The successful processing of these previously problematic waste materials into functional composites is a significant step forward in industrial waste recovery. The research demonstrates that materials previously destined for landfill or incineration can be transformed into useful products with measurable performance characteristics.

The superior flexural performance opens new market opportunities in the construction and building materials sector, where these recycled composites could be sold at premium price due to their enhanced structural properties rather than being limited to low value applications that would be typically associated with recycled content.

The processing methods developed through this research are scalable and compatible with existing industrial equipment, facilitating potential commercial implementation. The use of conventional twin screw extrusion and injection moulding processes ensures that the technology can be adopted by recycling facilities without requiring specialised equipment.

5.3 Contribution to Sustainable Materials Development

The comprehensive mechanical characterization has established baseline performance data for MPE/WTB composite systems, providing a foundation for future optimization work. The identification of poor interfacial bonding as the primary limitation provides clear direction for future research focusing on compatibilization strategies and surface treatment approaches.

The research demonstrates successful application of circular economy principles to industrial waste management, creating value from materials that would otherwise represent environmental liabilities. The alignment with European Union waste management directives and the growing regulatory pressure to eliminate composite waste landfilling makes this research particularly relevant for commercial implementation.

These materials behave differently depending on how they're loaded, performing exceptionally well under bending conditions but showing limitations when subjected to impact or tensile forces. This means they can be strategically selected for applications where their strengths align with the loading requirements

5.4 Foundation for Future Development

This research has established a solid foundation for future optimisation work. The systematic understanding of property composition relationships enables targeted development of compatibilization strategies, processing optimisation, and application specific material design. By clearly defining critical thresholds and understanding degradation mechanisms, this research establishes a systematic approach for overcoming current limitations via advanced surface treatment and compatibilization strategies.

The research has proven that the fundamental concept of incorporating wind turbine blade waste into polyolefin matrices is technically sound and practically achievable. This opens the door for advanced development work focused on optimising interfacial adhesion, controlling fibre distribution, and developing application specific formulations.

5.5 Broader Impact

By providing a viable end of life solution for wind turbine blades, this research helps address one of the key sustainability challenges facing the wind energy sector. The successful demonstration of waste to resource conversion provides a practical example of circular economy implementation that creates economic value while addressing environmental challenges.

This research offers valuable insights into addressing the global challenge of industrial waste management, while also promoting the advancement of renewable energy infrastructure. By presenting a viable end of life solution for wind turbine blades, it addresses one of the key sustainability challenges facing the wind energy sector. The successful demonstration of waste to resource conversion provides a practical example of circular economy implementation that creates economic value while addressing environmental challenges.

This research has established a strong foundation for future development through optimization of compatibilization strategies and the development of application specific formulations. The systematic approach demonstrated here can be extended to other industrial waste streams, contributing to the broader development of sustainable materials technologies.

In conclusion, this investigation has successfully achieved its primary objective of demonstrating the repeatability of recycling industrial waste into reusable products. The work provides immediate solutions for challenging waste management problems while establishing

a foundation for continued development in sustainable materials engineering. The combination of rigorous mechanical characterization, practical processing validation, and clear identification of future development pathways makes this research a valuable contribution to both academic understanding and industrial application of waste derived composite materials.

6. References

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